

Climate Changes and Natural Resources Sustainability Towards National Development

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ABSTRACT

Natural resources existence and sustainability is climate change dependent as changes in climatic conditions results in natural resources existence, shift, modification or exit from a given location on earth. Every town or countries development and sustenance is dependent on natural resources, mining and processing into usable products. Climate changes will continue to occur resulting in environmental changes because of human activities on the land and its fight for existence, sustenance, progress and success on planet earth. This research work sorts to investigate climate changes in Nsutem in the Eastern Region of Ghana, its effects on natural resources and its sustainability for national development. Research findings indicates that gold mining activities is destroying farmlands, forest reserves, lands and water resources which will result in changes in the climate in the future. Destruction of forests reserves and farmlands due to illegal gold mining will lead to changes in rainfall regimes over the region as evapotranspiration will reduce drastically in the future. This will have effect on future generation if care is not taken to protect, sustain and make use of the natural resources within the community in an efficient, sustainable and measurable manner. Illegal gold mining activities on water bodies is turning natural river channels into muddy areas and this will reduce evaporation from water bodies which is to contribute into the hydrological cycle for more rainfalls in the future.

Keywords: *climate changes, natural resources, sustainability, development, power bank, hydrological cycle, evaporation, land, forest reseves.*

1 Introduction

Changes in the climate has resulted in flooding and droughts worldwide. Severe flooding usually leads to breakage of dams and huge hydraulic structures yielding to

the loss of lives and properties worth Billions of US dollars each year. The global

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development community is looking for new solutions to traditional development issues such as economic stagnation, persistent poverty, hunger, malnutrition, and illness, as well as newer challenges like environmental degradation and globalization. One key approach that has received growing attention is the concept of sustainable development or 'development which lasts' (WCED, 1987). Due to differing hydrological cycle and the resultant severe precipitations over a region, engineers are developing sustainable structures which will help protect resources and human lives. Following the 1992 Earth Summit in Rio de Janeiro and the adoption of the United Nations' Agenda 21, the goal of sustainable development has become well accepted world-wide (UN, 1993). The threat of global climate change poses an unprecedented challenge to humanity and due to that man is fighting from all angles to combat climate change. While climate change is important in the long run, it is crucial to recognize that there are a number of other development issues that affect human welfare more immediately – such as hunger and malnutrition, poverty, health, and pressing local environmental issues. Climate change and sustainable development interact in a circular fashion and are therefore intertwined. Climate change will have an impact on prospects for sustainable development worldwide, and in turn, alternative development paths will certainly affect future climate change. Participatory

approach is one of the main ways by which climate change can be solved where all bodies within a country or worldwide are brought together with views and opinions shared and applied. Climate change is a menace which needs to be combated worldwide with all seriousness before it destroys lives. The global community needs to urgently and effectively address the two major challenges of the 21st century—sustainable development and climate change (Munashinghe, 2010). Global warming is unequivocal and almost certainly caused by recent human activities that have increased the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (IPCC, 2007; IAUR, 2009).

It is believed that the efficient and scrupulous use of natural resources including energy, water and materials, and the use of more renewable and clean energy—lie at the heart of climate change mitigation (Brabeck-Letmath, 2016). Some research carried out on this topic has provided us with supportive evidence, in-depth analysis, and even inspiration on feasible methods (Barrett and Scott 2011; Abdullah et al. 2014). By recognizing the importance of resource efficiency for mitigating climate change and maintaining sustainability, Nestlé has moved towards resource efficient, renewable energy-oriented and 'zero waste' production (Brabeck-Letmath, 2016).

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2 RESEARCH AREA

The research area for this study is in Nsutam in the Eastern Region of Ghana. The people of Nsutam are involved in gold mining, farming and trading. Some of the farm products produced includes coconut, cocoa, plantain, yam, cassava, sugar cane and all kinds of vegetables produced during the farming seasons. The huge amount of gold discovered in the community has resulted in all kinds of illegal gold mining activities destroying water bodies, forest reserves and lands. The community has a population of about 7000 (2021 population census) with the majority being immigrants due to the gold mining business, Linda Dor and Paradise Tourist operations in the community. The destroyed lands needs reclamation process in order to restore the infertile lands back into more fertile rich soils which will support plant growth in order to support the hydrological cycle, exchanges of oxygen and carbon dioxide between man and plants. Restoration of the degraded lands will also promote afforestation and wildlife existence in the future for future generation. It will also promote tourist attraction when vegetation's are groomed and protected with the existence of wildlife's. **Fig 1** below is a view of the study area in the Eastern Region of Ghana where coconut is in mild

production to boost livelihoods within the community.

Fig. 1: Map of Fanteakwa south district

3 Discussions of Research Findings

3.1 Climate changes within the study area

Daily changes in nature and the hydrological cycle is as a result of climate changes which is experienced all year round within the study area. Nsutam community in the Eastern Region of Ghana experiences different climate circumstances as a result of man's activities on land, air and water resources. Due to the gold mining activities within the community, there are all kinds of activities resulting in environmental factors changing the climate regime of the community. Gold mining activity have destroyed lands,

water bodies, forest reserves etc and this in turn have also affecting the hydrological cycle. Climate changes will continue to have effect on the community until there is a balance in the hydrological cycle. Clean water bodies, clean underground water and good evapotranspiration between plants and the atmosphere in the right proportion to contribute to rain formation and the resultant rainfall on land. Climate regime over the years within the study area have been in good shape until recently when man became too greedy and eager to be rich hence overexploitation of land and water resources to extract real gold. This has led to the destruction of water bodies, land and forest reserves hence a change in the hydrological cycle and the resultant climate changes.

3.2 Rainfall and dry seasonal patterns or regime

The study area has two season's namely rainy season and dry season throughout the year. It experiences two rainy season with the June and July rainfalls being the maximum over the entire region. The other one is the dry season which experiences no rainfall within the region. During this time, the entire plants over the land are seen dry with a high rate of evaporation on water resources and evapotranspiration on plants and grasses. The major farming

season is done during the rainy season where all kinds of farm produce are obtained in right proportion for the market and the homes. Because of the availability of rainfall within this period together with the rich lands, farm yields are high and this put money in the pocket of farmers and food on their tables. Dry season is also experienced with no rains within this period. There is no major farming activities within this period except visit to cocoa farm lands by cocoa farmers within the sub region. Small vegetable gardens and farms are mostly done within the dry season by irrigating with water from rivers such as River Birim but this has stopped. This is as a result of the destruction of the River Birim and River Spong in the community by illegal gold miners.

Bush burning is also an activity which is experienced once a while within the community especially during the dry season. Bush burning is usually through accidents and not like in the northern part of Ghana where people intentionally burn farmlands to obtain fresh green grass to feed their animals. During this period, cocoa farms get burnt together with other farmlands which depletes the pockets of cocoa farmers as they need to start all over the process of cocoa farming on the farmlands. Cocoa is a major crop which is produced within the community just

like coconut and this is boosting the economic status of the community. The climatic impact on cocoa is very good especially during the rainy season where rains are obtained in their right proportion to boost cocoa production hence resulting in high yields. Yields becomes very good in years where rainfall patterns are better. Low yields are obtained in times when rainfall patterns are very bad and this also affects other crop production within the Nsutam community.

3.3 Gold as a resources in Nsutem

Gold production within the sub – region started long enough with the 90s especially in Osino which is a neighboring town to Nsutam in the Eastern Region of Ghana. Gold production with the Nsutam community has been rampant in the 2020s with a lot of gold mining companies sited within the community. Even though they are not to international standards such as Newmont, Persus mines, Asante Gold fields etc., they are producing gold with hundreds of workers to boost the Nsutam community and Ghana as a whole. This has added to the two major earning activities within the community which is buses stop points at Linda Dor and Paradise. The inception of the gold mining activity has made the community a vibrant one with all kinds of immigrants seeking for greener

pastures to live within the community. Illegal gold mining is also done within the community to put money in the pockets of individuals. It's an advantage to put money in the pockets of individuals, give employments but is leading to the destruction of farmlands, forest reserves and water resources. The River Birim and Supong within the community which used to be a drinking water source, water for bathing, water for baptism by Christians, irrigation, washing is in a poor state as the quality has been deteriorated and cannot be used to meet such demands again. The illegal gold mining activities within the community are destroying lands and water bodies and needs government agencies to look into it and salvage the situation.

Plate 1: Degraded farmlands

The destruction of land resources and water bodies is so rampant and needs stringent action from government and agencies to abrogate the canker. Large cocoa farms which is a national treasure just like gold are being cleared on daily basis and the rich soils overexploited for gold underground. Think of the quantum of money that have been obtained or generated from cocoa business in Ghana for over ten years now. If building a gold mining business to Newmont Ahafo or Newmont Abirem standards, how many gold mines can be built from this money obtained from this cocoa business. Is cocoa business and its operation not a treasure and gold mining business then? Think of the hard work that has been done by foreigners, agriculturist, extension officers and ancestors who saw Cocoa as a treasure and started working on it. Think of the British, the Indians, Dutch, Germans, the Portugues and others who lived in Ghana years back and the work they did on this land? The Billions of dollars, Pounds Sterling, cedis, the revenue it has generated for Ghana over the years and its final destruction today by this current greedy generations. Water bodies and resources such as Supong, River Birim at Nsutam has been destroyed badly by these illegal gold miners and this water bodies are now turning into dry lands. It therefore calls for international bodies and countries interested in the gold mining business in Ghana to step in and save the land. It looks like foreigners in other African countries are interested in the big well established international gold mining companies and business in Ghana and hence using modern intelligence to take and rule Ghana gold mining business. And therefore the need to look at it. A lot of works and hard work has been done by

great white men and women in Ghana and outside Ghana towards the development of Ghana and world such as gold mining business in Ghana. This resource has been the target of other African countries and their white man's world in Ghana and hence doing all they can to topple the freedom and destroy natural resources.

Take Dubai for instance and look at the high rate of development and great works being done by the Indigenous and other foreigners towards development and progress of the country in this 21st Century. Consider the dry desert and the rate of development; beautiful buildings, drainage works, good roads, hotels, impervious surface creation, planting of trees, grasses and new vegetation towards combating negative effects of climate changes in the future and enhancing the hydrological cycle. I believe its possible such works was done years back and hence the beautiful vegetation, good rainfall regime, the availability of foods, animals etc. But illegal gold mining and interest by greedy men and women is destroying water resources, forest reserves, land resources by cutting down trees, cocoa farms, destroying farmlands and embaking on all kinds of illegal gold mining activities nation wide. This is seen most in the southern part of Ghana with a lot of water resources turned into dirty water with high rate of turbidity and sediments. The rate of borehole drilling is now rampat in the southern part of Ghana and this is depleting ground water. If these continues and all surface water bodies becomes dry lands, the hydrological cycle will be affected and hence the rainfall regime in the future. Since there will be no connection between ground water, surface water, water

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above, vegetations and resultant contribution into the hydrological cycle.

With this hard work and scenarios it gives a clear indication of works that has been done by foreigners or white men like Portugues, British (1867 – 1957), Dutch (1598 – 1872), Indians, Swedish (1650 -1663), Denmark - Norway (1663 – 1850), German(1682 – 1720) etc. The first large scale industrial gold mining in Ghana was the Ashanti Goldfields corporation and established in 1897. In considering this first gold mine establishment date and the dates of colonial masters inhabitation in Ghana, it gives a clear indication of works done by foreigners and colonial masters. So imagine all the remaining gold mines in Ghana is about pulling resources and intelligence from the Ashanti Goldfield mine towards establishing all other remaining gold mines in Ghana, who owns gold mines in Ghana in this 21st century? With this ascertainment, it gives a clear indication of works that has been done towards discovery of treasures and establishment of treasures in Ghana towards the development of Ghana and the world. Therefore looking at the way natural resources and treasures; land resources, water bodies, forest reserves, cocoa farms etc are being destroyed, it calls for stringent action and mediation by these colonial masters to save the resources and treasures. I think the intelligence in the gold mining business has been used in the establishment of gold mines in other countries toward the development of the world. And same for crops, food stuffs and other treasures from Africa to other parts of the world for development of such country. An example is cocoa in China now. As a researcher, gold mining engineer, water resources engineer,

physicists I think Ghana is under treat when it comes to usage, discovery and harnessing of resources and treasure to serve the country and world wide. And therefore intervention by owners and colonial masters.

When one looks at the migration rate and intelligence in Ghana, most established Ghanaians are leaving the country to foreign lands and leaving the country and rich resources in the hands of other African country nationals and the take over is going on intelligently where Ghana Gold will finally land in different hands. The migration issue has been enhanced better after the COVID – 19 impact. There is the need to look at this seriously and save Ghana and its rich resources which is serving the world and feeding now and future generations.

3.4 Water bodies as a resources (Surface water and ground water)

Sources of water exist within the community which is serving the community in diverse ways. Sources of water serving the community includes rain water, surface water (River Birim and Supong) and ground water. Rain water is experienced during the two rainy season within the year where all kinds of crops receive rains to boost crop production. Individual homes depends on such rain water to meet daily demands and needs. The other source of water is surface water which is obtained from River Birim and Supong within the Nsutam community. These two water bodies have been deteriorated as a result of water pollution from illegal gold mining activities within the

community. Most of the gold mining activities within the community are illegal mining (Galamsey) which are done on the water bodies or on lands. They makes use of the water from the water bodies and channel them for the gold mining operation (**Plate 2**). The two river bodies have been destroyed as a result of this activity by illegal gold miners and hence requires drastic effort to put the water bodies in shape for now and the future generation. Because of this people no longer fetch water from the water bodies but makes of underground water which is the third water sources within the community. Underground water is now the major source of water for the community after the destruction of the surface water bodies. Community indigenous are now making use of boreholes drinking water and wells to get water to meet daily demands and needs. This water is used for cooking, washing, bathing, cleaning, drinking etc. The destruction of surface water bodies is a worry as it gives no balance in the hydrological cycle. Surface water replenishes underground water hence needs to be kept in good shape and so does surface water also evaporates to contribute to rain formation in the sky to fall back unto the land. Hence there is the need to keep a balance between this three sources of water; surface water, ground water and water above for continuity of the hydrological cycle and in serving future generation. The climate changes over the

sub region therefore needs to be in the right proportion so that there is a balance in the hydrological cycle in other to have positive impacts on natural resources such as on lands, forest reserves and water bodies.

Plate 2: River Birim destroyed by illegal gold miners

3.5 Coconut as a food Resources adding to national development and generating income

One major activity within the community is coconut production and the selling of coconut fruits to make a living. Coconut is therefore being seen as a natural resources which is boosting the Nsutam community and generating thousands of cedis on daily basis. This activity has been over the years and still ongoing within the community. The living standard of the community used to be very low but has been lifted up as a result of gold mining activity within

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the community. Coconut production in Ghana is in minimal quantity but can be given a national boost status when produced in large quantities and refined into other products for export as detailed by *Danquah et. al.* Coconut has many purposes which includes for food, fuel, folk medicine, building materials, charcoal, cosmetics, oil for frying and anointing, drinks, making soaps, furniture making and used as materials to make a variety of products for furnishing and decoration. Since the unemployment rate within the community is very high, the gospel about producing coconut on large scale can be advertised of which small factories can be formed to refine the raw coconut into products which will boost the Nsutam community, Ghana and the world as a whole.

Plate 3: Destroyed forest reserves in the study area

3.6 Natural resources sustainability

Nsutam community has a lot of rich natural resources which needs to be harnessed in the right direction as well

as protect it for the future generation. Some of this natural resources are lands, water, gold, forest reserves, cocoa, coconuts etc. The mining of gold within the community is enriching lives and generating Billions of Pounds Sterling for Ghana and the world market. Despite the enrichment of lives, there is the need for the community and government to mine the resource in the right direction while sustaining the natural resources for unborn generations to come. In this regards, there is the need to use standard operating procedures to identify the resources and mine it for the betterment of mankind. In doing this, lands, forest reserves, water bodies management will be through stakeholder participation towards the sustainability of the natural resources. Natural resources identification and assessment hasn't been the mentality of Ghanaians but only improper way of harnessing it. Ghana as a country is rich in natural resources so is Nsutam community in the Eastern Region of Ghana. Nsutam a stopover community is now welcoming natural resources discoverers all over the world as its rich in all kinds of resources. One most important thing in all this is the sustainability of the resource for the now and future generation. Ghana lacks protection, maintenance, management and sustainability attitude among its

citizens and so can be seen at Nsutam community in the Eastern Region of Ghana. The natural resources available at Nsutam needs to be harnessed, mined and protected for the future. In doing this, the natural resource can be used to feed the current generation and future generation. It therefore calls on the government, government agencies, stakeholders and private investors to help in the maintenance and protection of natural resources within the community as they continue to mine and use to meet daily needs and demands. Some citizens do not have the use for today and keep for future attitude and this needs to be installed in their minds in order to protect and maintain the resources at Nsutam. The Ghanaian government needs to cultivate the attitude of resources estimation, protection and maintenance for the future generation. Government institutions such as Water resources commission, Environmental Protection Agency and Lands commission needs to look at resources allocation and the potential of private investors to make use and protect the resources before leasing out. By this private investors who buys lands in communities such as Nsutam will use standard operation procedures to harness resources such as gold whiles protecting lands, forest reserves and water bodies.

3.7 Impacts of climate changes on natural resources towards national development

The preservation, conservation and development of natural resources leads to the development of country and world yearly. Negative impacts of climate changes does affect the natural resources and hence its resultant impacts on national development and vice versa. Positive impacts of climate changes on natural resources due to conservation and preservation of natural resources such as land resources, water bodies, forest reserves, crops and plant species is very good for the development of country. Generating, creating and conservation of forest reserves improves the hydrological cycle through evapotranspiration process, gives timber to boost the economy, woods for construction and roofing houses. It creates an area or habitation which is suitable for different animals and species which serves as a source of game or food in the future. Such forest reserves are generated into Eco parks, tourist sites where there are animals and canopy walks to boost economy growth. Obtaining herbal medicines from generated plants and crops addresses diseases control and hence addressing SDG – 3, good health and wellbeing. Conservation and protection

of land resources also contributes to good crop production (addressing the sustainable development Goal (SDG) – 2, zero hunger). It also generates income for people (SDG 1 – No poverty) and for the government as there is export of goods and provision of services to other countries. Conservation of land resources and avoidance of illegal gold mining activities maintains the soil fertility and by that improves crop production and plant growth.

Illegal gold mining activities has destroyed a lot of water bodies in the study area and in Ghana in general. This has resulted in the use of ground water rather than surface water resulting in high rate of ground water abstraction and ground water depletion. The hydrological cycle comprising ground water, surface water, water above, land surfaces and all plants on lands is breaking gradually as all surface waters have been polluted with high rate of turbidity and sediments. But this same surface water in good condition in terms of quality and aesthetics is used to meet various demands; water for drinking, water for cooking, water for irrigation, hydropower generation, used in factories etc. So once all these surface water bodies have been polluted to a higher degree, a project like hydropower generation in future cannot

be met. A hydropower project in Ghana like the Akosombo hydropower is serving now and future generation because of the quality nature of the water. Think of the impacts on turbines as polluted water, turbid or water with a lot of sediments are runned through turbines. This same hydropower project can be mounted on some of these destroyed water bodies (River Densu, River Birim, River Ankobra, River Birim etc) after good engineering to generate electricity to be used in the homes and in factories to add up to existing energy sources in Ghana. Most parts, areas, communities or localities in Ghana are facing power crisis or power outages on daily basis including Nsutam community and this is not promoting business and economic development. Indigenous in Ghana therefore resorts to back up sources of energy like generator set, solar panels etc to promote activities and business. But the power crises still continues. ***From research, there should therefore be another additional source of energy to buttress what already exist to serve mankind in critical situations world wide. And this can be the manufacturing of power bank that can be used to power TV set, radio, blender, hair dryer, fridge, iron (for ironing cloths during critical moments or power outages) etc with a life span of 4 – 12hrs. This can be comparable to***

power bank for powering phones during power outages or critical moments for few hours.

By manufacturing *power Banks* devices or gadgets, short light offs or power outages problems can be solved to address immediate light energy needs world wide. And since the source for such energy sources devices will be electricity from hydropower generation, we need to protect and preserve water bodies and surface water resources by avoiding illegal gold mining businesses in the study area. This will lead to the avoidance of changes in the climate system and hence natural resources sustainability towards national development.

There is therefore the need to experience positive impacts of climate changes like increase in rainfall in the right proportion rather than negative impacts. This will adds up and improve surface water bodies to serve mankind like in Akosombo which is generating electricity to solve power problems in Ghana. This calls for the avoidance of all illegal gold mining activities in Ghana and the resultant negative impacts on environment and mankind. Negative impacts of climate changes will continue to pose threats to mankind with all kinds of negative impacts and hence the needed total avoidance in all directions and angles.

4 Conclusion

Climate changes are bound to occur as man continue to embark on all kinds of activities such as afforestation, deforestation, illegal gold mining, bush burning, etc on the earth. Changes in the climate will result in more rains or lesser rainfall over the Nsutam region as the year's proceeds. Gold mining activities within the community will continue to grow as man's quest for riches continue to grow. This will impacts land, forest reserves and water bodies, plants and crop production both positively and negatively. It will have a positive effect if miners and private investors makes use of standard operating procedures in the mining business. It will have a negative effect if illegal mining (Galamsey) continue to abound within the community. By this lands, forest reserves, water bodies such as river Birim and Supong which have been destroyed drastically will impact the hydrological cycle negatively. This will result in climate changes over the region and associated problems. There is the need for natural resources estimation, protection, good management and maintenance for the current and future generation. There is the need for stakeholder participation when it comes to the protection and maintenance of the resource within the community and in Ghana to meet future

demands. The people lack maintenance mentality and mindset hence the need for the government to establish agencies whose sole responsibility is to see to the protection, good management and maintenance of national resources for the now and future generations. Research findings indicates that little is being done by government and agencies to protect lands, forest reserves, water resources and other natural resources for the future generation. Even security forces are not enforcing laws to abrogate the illegal gold mining business in Ghana. Illegal gold miners are mounting excavators everywhere and destroying lands and properties all in search of the fine metal gold. We therefore need to have a good conscience, original creators mentality and view gold mining and production business from nature's perspective and protect the environment and natural resources for ourselves and future generations.

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